

PRESTRESSED CONCRETE GIRDER BRIDGE

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This report will present the design of a cast-in-place, post-tensioned concrete, multi-cell box girder bridge under combined torsion, shear and flexure, based on the geometry of an example from the California Department of Transportation [1]. Figure 1 shows the elevation view of the bridge used for this example. The total length of the three spans is 412' (125.6 m): the first span is 126' (38.4 m), the center span is 168' (51.2 m), and the third span is 118' (36.0 m).

Figure 1—Elevation view of the bridge.

Figure 2 presents the cross-section of the bridge. The total width of the bridge is 58'-10" (17.93 m). The bridge carries three 12' (3.7 m) traffic lanes, two 10' (3.0 m) shoulders and two 1'-5" (0.45 m) concrete edge barriers.

Figure 2—Cross-section of the bridge.

The loads that act on the bridge include the self-weight, load of the asphalt concrete (A.C.) wearing surface with a thickness of 3 in (75 mm), and the live load in accordance with AASHTO LRFD 2017 [3] HL-93 (design truck plus design lane load).

Bending Moment, shear and torsional moment envelopes for bridge example

Figure 3—Bending moment diagrams for separate load cases. Conversion: 1 kip-ft = 1.356 kNm, 1 ft = 0.31 m.

Figure 4—Shear diagrams for separate load cases. Conversion: 1 kip = 4.45 kN, 1 ft = 0.31 m.

Figure 5—Torsional moment diagrams for separate load cases. Conversion: 1 kip-ft = 1.356 kNm, 1 ft = 0.31 m.

Materials

Concrete

Initial and 28-day concrete strength that will be used for the design of the bridge.

$$f_{ci}' = 3500 \text{ psi} \quad (24.1 \text{ MPa})$$

$$f_c' = 5000 \text{ psi} \quad (34.5 \text{ MPa})$$

$$\gamma_c = 0.15 \text{ kcf} \quad (23.6 \text{ kN/m}^3)$$

Modulus of Elasticity of concrete

$$E_c = 33,000 \gamma_c^{1.5} \sqrt{f_c'}$$

$$E_c = 4287 \text{ ksi} \quad (29.6 \text{ GPa})$$

Reinforcing steel

$$f_y = 60 \text{ ksi} \quad (414 \text{ MPa})$$

$$E_s = 29,000 \text{ ksi} \quad (200 \text{ GPa})$$

Prestressing steel

$$f_{pu} = 270 \text{ ksi} \quad (1862 \text{ MPa})$$

$$f_{py} = 243 \text{ ksi} \quad (1675 \text{ MPa})$$

$$f_{pj} = 202.5 \text{ ksi} \quad (1396 \text{ MPa})$$

Design computations for flexure according to AASHTO LRFD 2017 [3]

The following steps will be used for the design of the example bridge in flexure:

Step 1. Determine the tendon profile.

The tendon profile should be chosen so that the points of maximum eccentricities will occur at the points of maximum moments. The tendon profile should include the radius of the parabolas, points of inflexion along the cross section and distances from the C.G. of the cross section to points of maximum eccentricities.

Figure 6—Prestressing tendon profile along bridge length

Step 2. Determine the balancing forces and balancing bending moments

The balancing bending moments for each one of the sections of the cable path is determined.

$$q_p = \frac{8P_j f}{l^2}$$

First parabola: (From 0 ft to 110 ft)

$$q_{p1} = \frac{8P_j f}{l^2} = \frac{8 \times 1 \text{ kip} \times 3.05 \text{ ft}}{(110 \text{ ft})^2} = 2.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kip/ft}$$

Second parabola: (From 110 ft to 148 ft)

$$q_{p2} = \frac{8P_j f}{l^2} = \frac{8 \times 1 \text{ kip} \times 0.72 \text{ ft}}{(38 \text{ ft})^2} = 4.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kip/ft}$$

Third parabola: (From 148 ft to 272 ft)

$$q_{p3} = \frac{8P_j f}{l^2} = \frac{8 \times 1 \text{ kip} \times 3.16 \text{ ft}}{(124 \text{ ft})^2} = 1.64 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kip/ft}$$

Fourth parabola: (From 272 ft to 308 ft)

$$q_{p4} = \frac{8P_j f}{l^2} = \frac{8 \times 1 \text{ kip} \times 0.66 \text{ ft}}{(36 \text{ ft})^2} = 4.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kip/ft}$$

Fifth parabola: (From 308 ft to 412 ft)

$$q_{p5} = \frac{8P_j f}{l^2} = \frac{8 \times 1 \text{ kip} \times 3.11 \text{ ft}}{(104 \text{ ft})^2} = 2.30 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kip/ft}$$

These forces should be distributed over the whole width of the bridge, for this calculation the overhanging flanges are not taken into account and a mean value of the width of 50.5 ft, between the upper and lower flanges is used, to count for the skewed exterior girders.

$$q_{P1} = 4.00 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kip/ft}^2$$

$$q_{P2} = 7.90 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kip/ft}^2$$

$$q_{P3} = 3.25 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kip/ft}^2$$

$$q_{P4} = 8.10 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kip/ft}^2$$

$$q_{P5} = 4.55 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kip/ft}^2$$

Figure 7—Balancing moments from prestressing. Conversion: 1 kip-ft = 1.356 kNm, 1 ft = 0.31 m.

Step 3. Calculate the prestressing losses according with Section 5.9.3.

Calculation of Friction Losses:

For the calculation of friction losses, the friction coefficient is calculated based on the following equation:

$$\alpha_{Fl} = e^{-(\mu \cdot \theta + kv)}$$

$$\mu = 0.25 \text{ and } k = 0.0002$$

The angular friction coefficient α_{Fl} is calculated taking into account different sections of the parabolic profile of the tendon, in this example this sections are taken based on the parabolic changes of the profile. Then the following equation is used for computing the angle θ .

$$\theta = \frac{2y_{ij}}{l_{ij}}$$

Then the cumulative coefficient is calculated adding the values of angular coefficients obtained for each section.

Table—1, presents the cumulative angular force coefficients for Two-End stressing

Table 1—Cumulative angular force coefficients for two-end stressing

LOCATION	LEFT END STRESSING	RIGHT END STRESSING
0 ft - 50 ft	1	1
50 ft – 110 ft	0,966	0.965
110 ft – 126 ft	0,924	0.922
126 ft – 148 ft	0.906	0.905
148 ft – 210 ft	0.880	0.880
210 ft – 272 ft	0.843	0.843
272 ft – 294 ft	0.806	0.805
294 ft – 308 ft	0.780	0.780
308 ft – 365 ft	0.764	0.761
365 ft – 412 ft	0.721	0.720

Losses due to Elastic shortening:

The elastic shortening is computed based on a value of $\Delta f_{pES} = 3$ ksi. As used by the California Department of Transportation [1].

It is then converted into a force coefficient:

$$\Delta FC_{pES} = \frac{\Delta f_{pES}}{f_{ps}} = \frac{3ksi}{202.5ksi} = 0.015$$

Losses due to Anchor set:

For the losses due to Anchor set the following value is used:

$$\Delta FC_{pA} = 0.097$$

Time-dependant losses: Concrete Shrinkage and Creep

To calculate the losses due to concrete shrinkage, the strain due to shrinkage is calculated using the following equation:

$$\varepsilon_{sh} = k_s k_{hs} k_f k_{td} 0.48 \times 10^{-3} = 4.54 \times 10^{-4}$$

And the losses due to shrinkage are calculated with:

$$\Delta f_{pSH} = \varepsilon_{sh} \cdot E_p \cdot k_{df} = 13.585ksi$$

In the case of creep, the creep coefficient is calculated as follows:

$$\psi(t, t_i) = 1.9 k_s k_{hc} k_f k_{td} t_i^{-0.118} = 1.213$$

And the losses due to creep are calculated with:

$$\Delta f_{pSH} = \frac{E_p}{E_c} \cdot 0.66 \cdot \psi(t, t_i) \cdot k_{df} = 6.264ksi$$

As an assumption $\Delta f_{pR} = 2.4ksi$

The total time-dependant losses converted into a force coefficient are:

$$\Delta f_{TI} = \frac{\Delta f_{pSH} + \Delta f_{pCR} + \Delta f_{pR}}{f_{ps}} = 0.11$$

Finally the total losses of prestressing considering: friction, anchor set, elasting shortening and time dependant losses is computed with the following equation:

$$FC = \left(1 - \frac{\sum \Delta f_i}{f_{ps}} \right)$$

To simplify the example, the losses will be turned into a percentage of the initial prestressing force. So finally a total loss of 25% of the total load will be used for calculations.

Step 4. Check stresses at Service Flexure (considering just DC and PT)

Service flexure will just consider the effects of the Dead Load (DC) and prestressing force (PT), that are the force acting as soon as the bridge is terminated, it not includes the effects produced by the wearing surface (DW) and the Live Load (LL).

The allowable stresses are the following:

Table 2—Allowable stresses at Service Flexure

Force	Stress limit
Compression	0.60 f'ci = 2.1(ksi) 14.5(MPa)
Tension	No tension allowed

The stresses will be computed at different positions along the bridge length:

Table 3—Calculated stresses at Service Flexure

Length (ft)	Stresses at top of section (ksi)	Length (ft)	Stresses at bottom of section (ksi)
0	0.643	0	0.643
50	0.468	50	0.868
110	1.675	110	0.689
126	0.892	126	0.964
148	1.214	148	0.686
210	0.632	210	0.657
272	1.155	272	0.724
294	0.939	294	1.024
308	1.752	308	0.718
365	0.388	365	0.971
412	0.643	412	0.643

Step 5. Check the stresses at Service Limit State (SLS III) before losses, allowing the stress limit provided in Section 5.9.2.3.1a for compression and Table 5.9.2.3.1b-1 for tension.

Service Limit State (SLS III) uses the following load combination DC + DW +0.8LL, considering the whole effects of the load at normal operational service. Here the effects of prestressing losses will not be considered:

The allowable stresses are the following:

Table 4—Allowable stresses at Service III (without losses)

Force	Stress limit	
Compression	$0.60 f'_c = 3.0(ksi)$	30.7(MPa)
Tension	$0.19\lambda\sqrt{f'_c} = 0.425ksi$	2.9 (MPa)

Table 5—Calculated stresses at Service III (without losses)

Length (ft)	Stresses at top of section (ksi)	Length (ft)	Stresses at bottom of section (ksi)
0	0.643	0	0.643
50	0.725	50	0.538
110	0.833	110	0.399
126	0.752	126	0.502
148	0.750	148	0.506
210	0.951	210	0.246
272	0.708	272	0.560
294	0.691	294	0.581
308	0.820	308	0.415
365	0.620	365	0.673
412	0.643	412	0.643

Step 6. Check stresses at Service Limit State (SLS III) after losses allowing the stress limit provided in Table 5.9.2.3.2a-1 for compression and Table 5.9.2.3.2b-1 for tension.

Service Limit State (SLS III) uses the following load combination DC + DW +0.8LL, considering the whole effects of the load at normal operational service. The effects of prestressing losses are considered in this case, previously a 25% losses was calculated, hence this value will be used to reduce the total jacking force P_j .

The allowable stresses are the following:

Table 6—Allowable stresses at Service III (with Losses)

Force	Stress limit	
Compression	$0.60 f'_c = 3.0(ksi)$	30.7(MPa)
Tension	$0.19\lambda\sqrt{f'_c} = 0.425ksi$	2.9 (MPa)

Table 7—Allowable stresses at Service III (with Losses)

Length (ft)	Stresses at top of section (ksi)	Length (ft)	Stresses at bottom of section (ksi)
0	0.643	0	0.643
50	0.887	50	0.329
110	0.975	110	0.215
126	1.093	126	0.064
148	0.830	148	0.402
210	1.129	210	0.017
272	0.784	272	0.461
294	1.028	294	0.147
308	0.976	308	0.215
365	0.780	365	0.467
412	0.643	412	0.643

Design computations according to ACI 318-14 [2]

Step 1: Determine the factored bending moment, shear force, and torsional moment at the face of Bent 2 of the box-girder based on the load combinations of Article 5.3.1.

$$M_u^- = 56804.2kip - ft \quad (77016kN - m) \text{ at the face of Bent 1}$$

$$M_u^- = 44485.1kip - ft \quad (60314kN - m) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$V_u = 3035kip \quad (13500.5kN) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$T_u = 12108kip - ft \quad (16416.5kN - m) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

Step 2: Determine the section properties and material properties

Table 8—Section properties (ACI318-14)

A_{cp}	44637 in ²	2.9×10^7 mm ²
p_{cp}	1275 in	32385 mm
A_g	13684 in ²	8.8×10^6 mm ²
d	64.8 in	1646 mm
d_s	77in	1956 mm
b_w	60 in	1524 mm
A_{oh}	41710 in ²	2.7×10^7 mm ²
p_h	1250 in	31750 mm
β_1	0.80	
γ_p	0.28	

Step 3: Check the flexural resistance for the tendon layout shown in Fig. 6, based on the factored bending moment produced at the face of Bent 2.

$$\frac{M_u}{\phi} = A_{ps} f_{ps} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2} \right)$$

$$A_{ps} = \frac{P_j}{f_{pj}} = \frac{9300kips}{202.5ksi} = 46in^2 \quad \rho_p = \frac{A_{ps}}{A_g} = 0.00336$$

$$f_{ps} = f_{pu} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma_p}{\beta_1} \times \rho_p \times \frac{f_{pu}}{f_c'} \right) = 252.9ksi \quad a = \frac{A_{ps} \times f_{pu}}{0.85 f_c' \times b} = 5.64in$$

$$M_n = 46in^2 \times 252.9ksi \left(64.8in - \frac{5.64in}{2} \right) = 59982kip - ft \quad (81325kN - m)$$

$$\phi M_n = M_u$$

$$0.90 \times 59982kip - ft = 53983kip - ft \quad (73193kN - m)$$

Step 4: Compute the additional mild steel required for flexure

$$\frac{M_u}{\phi} = A_{ps} f_{ps} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2} \right) + A_s f_y \left(d - \frac{a}{2} \right)$$

$$\text{Assuming : } A_s = 30in^2 \quad (19355mm^2) \quad \rho_l = \frac{A_s}{A_g} = 0.00219$$

$$f_{ps} = f_{pu} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma_p}{\beta_1} \left(\rho_p \times \frac{f_{pu}}{f_c'} + \frac{d_s}{d_p} \times \frac{f_y}{f_c'} \times \rho_l \right) \right) = 249.9ksi \quad a = \frac{A_{ps} \times f_{pu} + A_s \times f_y}{0.85 f_c' \times b} = 6.46in$$

$$\phi M_n = 62959.2 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (85361.2 \text{ kN-m})$$

This area of reinforcement will correspond to 39 #8 (25 mm) bars.

Step 5: Check if torsion can be neglected based on Article 22.7.4

$$T_{th} = \lambda \sqrt{f_c'} \left(\frac{A_g^2}{P_{cp}} \right) \sqrt{1 + \frac{f_{pc}}{4\lambda \sqrt{f_c'}}$$

$$f_{pc} = \frac{P_j}{A}$$

$$T_{th} = 1 \times \sqrt{5 \text{ ksi}} \times \left(\frac{(13684 \text{ in}^2)^2}{1275 \text{ in}} \right) \times \sqrt{1 + \frac{9300 \text{ ksi} / 13392 \text{ in}^2}{4 \times 1 \times \sqrt{5 \text{ ksi}}}} = 1609 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (2182 \text{ kN-m})$$

In this case $T_{th} < T_u$, so torsional effects should be considered for the design, and the factored torsional moment should be used.

Step 6: Check if the dimensions of the cross-section are adequate based on Article 22.7.7.1.

$$\left(\frac{V_u}{b_w d} \right) + \left(\frac{T_u}{1.7 A_{oh} t} \right) \leq \phi \left(\frac{V_c}{b_w d} + 8 \sqrt{f_c'} \right)$$

$$V_c = (0.6 \lambda \sqrt{f_c'} + 700) b_w d = (0.6 \times 1 \times \sqrt{5000 \text{ psi}} + 700) \times 60 \text{ in} \times 64.8 \text{ in} = 2887 \text{ kips} \quad (12842 \text{ kN})$$

$$V_c = 5 \lambda \sqrt{f_c'} b_w d = 5 \times 1 \times \sqrt{5000 \text{ psi}} \times 60 \text{ in} \times 64.8 \text{ in} = 1375 \text{ kips} \quad (6116 \text{ kN})$$

$$\left(\frac{V_u}{b_w d} \right) + \left(\frac{T_u}{1.7 A_{oh} t} \right) = \left(\frac{2991 \text{ kip}}{60 \text{ in} \times 64.8 \text{ in}} \right) + \left(\frac{10896 \text{ kip-ft}}{1.7 \times 41710 \text{ in} \times 12 \text{ in}} \right) = 0.866 \text{ ksi} \quad (5.97 \text{ MPa})$$

$$\phi \left(\frac{V_c}{b_w d} + 8 \sqrt{f_c'} \right) = 0.75 \left(\frac{1375 \text{ kips}}{60 \text{ in} \times 64.8 \text{ in}} + 8 \sqrt{5000 \text{ psi}} \right) = 0.690 \text{ ksi} \quad (4.76 \text{ MPa})$$

Since $0.866 \text{ ksi} \quad (5.97 \text{ MPa}) > 0.690 \text{ ksi} \quad (4.76 \text{ MPa})$, the size of the cross-section is not adequate and the dimensions should be increased. By an iterative procedure, it is determined that the new $b_w = 86 \text{ in}$ (2184 mm). All vertical girders will be flared. Exterior girders will now have a thickness $t = 19 \text{ in}$ (483 mm) and interior girders $t = 16 \text{ in}$ (407 mm).

$$M_u^- = 44470 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (60293.3 \text{ kN-m}) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$V_u = 3035 \text{ kip} \quad (13500.5 \text{ kN}) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$V_c = (0.6 \lambda \sqrt{f_c'} + 700) b_w d = 4137.4 \text{ kips} \quad (18404 \text{ kN})$$

$$V_c = 5 \lambda \sqrt{f_c'} b_w d = 1970 \text{ kips} \quad (8763 \text{ kN})$$

$$\left(\frac{V_u}{b_w d} \right) + \left(\frac{T_u}{1.7 A_{oh} t} \right) = 0.634 \text{ ksi} \quad (4.37 \text{ MPa})$$

$$\phi \left(\frac{V_c}{b_w d} + 8 \sqrt{f_c'} \right) = 0.690 \text{ ksi} \quad (4.76 \text{ MPa})$$

Now $0.690 \text{ ksi} \quad (4.76 \text{ MPa}) > 0.634 \text{ ksi} \quad (4.37 \text{ MPa})$, and the size of the cross-section is adequate.

Step 7: Calculate the required area of transverse reinforcement for shear based on Article 22.5.10.5

$$\frac{A_v}{s} = \frac{V_u - \phi V_c}{\phi f_y d}$$

$$\frac{A_v}{s} = \frac{3035 \text{kip} - 0.75 \times 1970 \text{kip}}{0.75 \times 60 \text{ksi} \times 64.8 \text{in}} = 0.56 \text{in}^2/\text{in} \quad \left(14.23 \text{mm}^2/\text{mm}\right)$$

The area of reinforcement required will be placed in the 5 webs of the cross-section. Therefore using #5 (16 mm) two-legged stirrups for each of the 5 webs gives:

$$A_v = 2 \times 5 \times \frac{\pi \left(\frac{5}{8}\right)^2}{4} = 3.1 \text{in}^2 \quad (2000 \text{mm}^2)$$

$$s = \frac{3.1 \text{in}^2}{0.56 \text{in}^2/\text{in}} = 5.54 \text{in} \quad (141 \text{mm})$$

For shear, the required transverse reinforcement is #5 (16 mm) bars at 5.50 in (140 mm) on center.

Step 8: Calculate the required area of transverse reinforcement for shear in the exterior webs based on Article 22.5.10.

The factored shear force for the left exterior girder considering the additional self-weight of the larger section is 782 kips (3479 kN).

$$V_c = 5\lambda\sqrt{f_c'}b_wd = 5 \times 1 \times \sqrt{5000 \text{psi}} \times 19 \text{in} \times 64.8 \text{in} = 435 \text{kips} \quad (1935 \text{kN})$$

$$\left(\frac{V_u}{b_wd}\right) + \left(\frac{T_u}{1.7A_{oh}t}\right) = 0.682 \text{ksi} \quad (4.70 \text{MPa})$$

$$\phi \left(\frac{V_c}{b_wd} + 8\sqrt{f_c'}\right) = 0.690 \text{ksi} \quad (4.76 \text{MPa})$$

Here, 0.690 ksi (4.76 MPa) > 0.682 ksi (4.70 MPa). As such, the size of the exterior webs is adequate.

$$\frac{A_v}{s} = \frac{782 \text{kip} - 0.75 \times 435 \text{kip}}{0.75 \times 60 \text{ksi} \times 64.8 \times (\cos 27^\circ)} = 0.16 \text{in}^2/\text{in} \quad \left(4.07 \text{mm}^2/\text{mm}\right)$$

Using 2 legs of #5 (16 mm) stirrups per web, the required spacing becomes.

$$A_v = 2 \times \frac{\pi \left(\frac{5}{8}\right)^2}{4} = 0.61 \text{in}^2 \quad (2000 \text{mm}^2)$$

$$s = \frac{0.61 \text{in}^2}{0.16 \text{in}^2/\text{in}} = 3.82 \text{in} \quad (97 \text{mm})$$

For the right exterior girder the same area reinforcement at the same spacing will be provided. To conclude, for shear in the exterior webs, the required transverse reinforcement is #5 (16 mm) bars at 3.75 in (95 mm) on center.

Step 9: Calculate the required area of transverse reinforcement for torsion based on Article 22.7.6.

$$\frac{A_t}{s} = \frac{T_u}{\phi 2A_o f_y \cot \theta \cos \alpha} = \frac{12107.8 \text{kip} - \text{ft}}{0.75 \times 2 \times 0.85 \times 41710 \text{in}^2 \times 60000 \text{psi} \times \cot(37.5^\circ) \times \cos(27^\circ)}$$

$$\frac{A_t}{s} = 0.04 \text{in}^2/\text{in} \quad \left(1.00 \text{mm}^2/\text{mm}\right)$$

Step 10: Calculate the required area of transverse reinforcement for exterior girders considering the effects of shear and torsion

$$\left(\frac{A_v}{s} + \frac{A_t}{s}\right) = 0.16 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} + 0.04 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} = 0.20 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(5.08 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm}\right)$$

$$s = \frac{0.61 \text{ in}^2}{0.20 \text{ in}^2/\text{in}} = 3.10 \text{ in} \text{ (79 mm)}$$

For the exterior (skewed) webs, the provided transverse reinforcement becomes two-legged #5 (16 mm) stirrups at 3 in (75 mm) on center. For the internal (vertical) webs, the required transverse reinforcement remains two-legged #5 (16 mm) stirrups at 5 in. (125 mm) on center.

Step 11: Calculate the transverse reinforcement in the flanges for torsion only based on Article 22.7.6.1.

$$\frac{A_t}{s} = \frac{T_u}{\phi 2A_o f_y \cot \theta} = \frac{12107.8 \text{ kip-ft}}{0.75 \times 2 \times 0.85 \times 41710 \text{ in}^2 \times 60000 \text{ psi} \times \cot(37.5)}$$

$$\frac{A_t}{s} = 0.035 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.89 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm}\right)$$

$$A_v = 2 \times \frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{3}{8}\right)^2 = 0.22 \text{ in}^2 \left(143 \text{ mm}^2\right)$$

$$s = \frac{0.22 \text{ in}^2}{0.035 \text{ in}^2/\text{in}} = 6.30 \text{ in} \text{ (160 mm)}$$

The provided transverse reinforcement for the flanges consists of two stirrup legs of #3 (10 mm) bars at 6.25 in. (160 mm) on center.

Step 12: Check the maximum spacing for shear and torsion transverse reinforcement based on Articles 9.7.6.2.2 and 9.7.6.3.3

§9.7.6.2.2 states that the spacing for transverse reinforcement provided for shear shall not be larger than the minimum between $d = 64.8$ in (1646 mm) or 12 in (305 mm). §9.7.6.3.3 limits the spacing for transverse torsional reinforcement to a value no larger than the minimum of $p_h = 1250$ in (31750 mm) or 12 in (305 mm). For the interior webs, a spacing of 5.50 in (140 mm) was used, which fulfils this requirement. For the exterior webs, a spacing of 3 in (75 mm) was used, which fulfils this requirement. For the flanges, a spacing of 6.25 in (160 mm) was used, which fulfils this requirement.

Step 13: Calculate the required area of longitudinal reinforcement for torsion based on Article 22.7.6.1.

$$A_t = \frac{A_t}{s} p_h \left(\frac{f_{yv}}{f_{yl}}\right) \cot^2 \theta = 0.04 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \times 1250 \text{ in} \times 1 \times \cot^2 37.5 = 83.3 \text{ in}^2 \left(53742 \text{ mm}^2\right)$$

As longitudinal reinforcement for torsion, #8 (25 mm) bars are used. The required number of bars required:

$$\#bars = \frac{A_t}{Arebar} = \frac{83.3 \text{ in}^2}{0.79 \text{ in}^2} \approx 106bars$$

Step 14: Check minimum required longitudinal and transverse reinforcement.

$$\left(\frac{A_v}{s} + \frac{A_t}{s}\right)_{\min} = 0.75\sqrt{f_c'} \frac{b_w}{f_{yt}} = 0.75 \times \sqrt{5000 \text{ psi}} \times \frac{86 \text{ in}}{60000 \text{ psi}} = 0.076 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \quad (1.93 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm})$$

$$A_{t,\min} = \frac{5\sqrt{f_c'} A_g}{f_y} - \left(\frac{A_t}{s}\right) p_h \frac{f_{yt}}{f_y} = \frac{5 \times \sqrt{5000 \text{ psi}} \times 9822 \text{ in}^2}{60000 \text{ psi}} - 0.0391 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \times 1250 \text{ in} \times 1 = 13.8 \text{ in}^2 \quad (8903.2 \text{ mm}^2)$$

$$A_{t,\min} = \frac{5\sqrt{f_c'} A_{cp}}{f_y} - \left(\frac{25b_w}{f_{yt}}\right) p_h \frac{f_{yt}}{f_y} = \frac{5 \times \sqrt{5000 \text{ psi}} \times 9822 \text{ in}^2}{60000 \text{ psi}} - \left(\frac{25 \times 86 \text{ in}}{60000 \text{ psi}}\right) \times 1250 \text{ in} \times 1 = 13.1 \text{ in}^2 \quad (8451.6 \text{ mm}^2)$$

Design computations according to EN 1992-1-1:2004 [4]

Step 1: Determine the factored bending moment, shear force, and torsional moment at the face of Bent 2 of the box-girder based on the load combinations

$$M_u^- = 61102.3 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (82844 \text{ kN-m}) \text{ at the face of Bent 1}$$

$$M_u^- = 47741.3 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (64715 \text{ kN-m}) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$V_u = 3162.2 \text{ kip} \quad (14066.2 \text{ kN}) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$T_u = 11354 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (15394 \text{ kN-m}) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

Step 2: Determine the section properties and material properties

Table 9—Section and material properties EN 1992-1-1:2004

SECTION PROPERTIES		
A_{cp}	44637 in ²	$2.9 \times 10^7 \text{ mm}^2$
p_{cp}	1275 in	32385 mm
A_g	13684 in ²	$8.8 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^2$
d	64.8 in	1646 mm
d_s	77 in	1956 mm
b_w	60 in	1524 mm
A_{oh}	41710 in ²	$2.7 \times 10^7 \text{ mm}^2$
p_h	1250 in	31750 mm
MATERIAL PROPERTIES		
λ	1	
γ_c	1.50	
γ_s	1.15	
$f_{p,ud}$	235 ksi	1620.3 Mpa
$f_{y,d}$	52.2 ksi	360 Mpa
$f'_{c,d}$	3.33 ksi	23 Mpa
$f_{p0.1k}$	243 ksi	1676 Mpa
$f_{p,d}$	211.3 ksi	1457 Mpa

Step 3: Check the flexural resistance for the tendon layout shown in Fig. 6, based on the factored bending moment produced at the face of Bent 2.

$$M_n = A_{ps} f_{pd} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2} \right)$$

$$A_{ps} = \frac{P_j}{f_{pj}} = \frac{9300 \text{ kips}}{202.5 \text{ ksi}} = 46 \text{ in}^2 \quad \rho_p = \frac{A_{ps}}{A_g} = 0.00336$$

$$a = \frac{A_{ps} \times f_{pd}}{\lambda f_c' \times b} = 5.63 \text{ in}$$

$$M_n = 46in^2 \times 211.3ksi \left(64.8in - \frac{5.63in}{2} \right) = 50127kip-ft \quad (67963.1kN-m)$$

Step 4: Compute the additional mild steel required for flexure

$$M_n = A_{ps} f_{pd} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2} \right) + A_s f_y \left(d - \frac{a}{2} \right)$$

$$\text{Assuming : } A_s = 40in^2 \quad (25806.4mm^2)$$

$$a = \frac{A_{ps} \times f_{pd} + A_s \times f_y}{\lambda f_c' \times b} = 6.84in$$

$$M_n = 62433.2kip-ft \quad (84648kN-m)$$

This area of reinforcement will correspond to 51 #8 (25 mm) bars.

Step 5: Verify if transverse reinforcement must be provided

$$C_{rdc} = \frac{0.18}{\gamma_c} = 0.12 \quad k_{EN} = 1 + \sqrt{\frac{200mm}{d(mm)}} = 1.35 \quad \rho_l = \frac{A_{ps}}{b_w \times d} = 0.012 \quad \sigma_{cp} = \frac{P_j}{A_g} = 0.68ksi$$

$$V_{rdc} = \left(C_{rdc} \cdot k \left(100 \cdot \rho_l \cdot f_c' \right)^{1/3} + k1 \cdot \sigma_{cp} \right) b_w \cdot d = 710.3kips(3160kN)$$

Since $V_u > V_{rdc}$ transverse reinforcement for shear must be provided.

Step 6: Compute the maximum and minimum shear reinforcement

$$\rho_{w,min} = \frac{0.08 \sqrt{f_c'}}{1.2 f_y} = 0.00095$$

$$A_{v,min} = \rho_{w,min} \cdot b_w = 0.057in^2 (36.77mm^2)$$

$$\alpha_c = 1 + \frac{\sigma_{cp}}{f_{cd}} = 1.204 \quad \nu = 0.6 \left(1 - \frac{f_c'}{250MPa} \right) = 0.52$$

$$A_{v,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot \nu \cdot b_w \cdot f_c'}{2 \cdot f_{yd}} = 1.194in^2 (770.32mm^2)$$

Step 7: Compute the maximum shear resistance

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45°, 35° and 22°.

For $\theta = 45^\circ$.

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot \nu \cdot f_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 3631.8kips(16155.1kN)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$.

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot \nu \cdot f_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 3412.7kips(15180.5kN)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$.

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot \nu \cdot f_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 2522.8kips(11222kN)$$

Step 8: Compute the design torsional resistance moment

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45°, 35° and 22°.

For $\theta = 45^\circ$.

$$T_{rd,max} = 2\nu \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 73593 \text{kip-ft} (99779 \text{kN-m})$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$.

$$T_{rd,max} = 2\nu \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 69155 \text{kip-ft} (93762 \text{kN-m})$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$.

$$T_{rd,max} = 2\nu \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 51122 \text{kip-ft} (69312 \text{kN-m})$$

Step 9: Verify if the cross section is adequate

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45°, 35° and 22°.

For $\theta = 45^\circ$.

$$\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.0$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$.

$$\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.1$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$.

$$\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.5$$

Cross section is adequate if: $\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} \leq 1.0$

Therefore when assuming that $\theta = 35^\circ$ and 22° the inequality is not fulfilled so the section should be enlarged. This process could be done by iteration, finally the sections are changed and the inequality is checked one more time.

For $\theta = 35^\circ$ and $b_w = 62 \text{in}$ and $t_f = 13 \text{in}$.

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot \nu \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 3526.5 \text{kips} (15687 \text{kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2\nu \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 74917.5 \text{kip-ft} (101574.5 \text{kN-m})$$

$$\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.0$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$ and $b_w = 84\text{in}$ and $t_f = 18\text{in}$.

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 3532\text{kips}(15711.1\text{kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 76683\text{kip} - \text{ft}(103968.2\text{kN} - \text{m})$$

$$\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.0$$

Step 10. Compute the required shear reinforcement

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45° , 35° and 22° .

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_v/s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 1.04\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(26.4\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$A_v/s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.73\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(18.5\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$A_v/s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.42\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(10.7\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 11. Design shear reinforcement for outside skewed girders

$$V_{u,ext} = 770.4\text{kips} (3427\text{kN})$$

Step 11.1. Verify if transverse reinforcement must be provided

$$V_{rdc} = \left(C_{rdc} \cdot k \left(100 \cdot \rho_l \cdot f'_c \right)^{1/3} + k_1 \cdot \sigma_{cp} \right) t_f \cdot d = 142.1\text{kips}(632.1\text{kN})$$

Therefore, transverse reinforcement for shear in the form of two legged stirrups must be provided.

Step 11.2. Compute the minimum and maximum shear reinforcement

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45° , 35° and 22° .

For $\theta = 45^\circ$, $t_f = 12\text{in}$

$$A_{v,min} = \rho_{w,min} \cdot t_f = 0.0114\text{in}^2 (7.4\text{mm}^2)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$, $t_f = 12\text{in}$

$$A_{v,min} = \rho_{w,min} \cdot t_f = 0.0123\text{in}^2 (8.0\text{mm}^2)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$, $t_f = 18\text{in}$

$$A_{v,min} = \rho_{w,min} \cdot t_f = 0.017\text{in}^2 (11.0\text{mm}^2)$$

Step 11.3. Check if cross-sections are adequate

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45°, 35° and 22°.

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 726.4 \text{ kips} (3231.2 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 73593 \text{ kip} - \text{ft} (99779 \text{ kN} - \text{m})$$

$$0.5 \frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.14$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 739.4 \text{ kips} (3289 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 74917.5 \text{ kip} - \text{ft} (101574.5 \text{ kN} - \text{m})$$

$$0.5 \frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.12$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 756.8 \text{ kips} (3366.4 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 76683 \text{ kip} - \text{ft} (103968.2 \text{ kN} - \text{m})$$

$$0.5 \frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.10$$

On each one of the cases, the cross section of the outer webs are not adequate for resisting the required factored forces. Therefore the cross sections are increased iterating until the inequality is satisfied.

For $\theta = 45^\circ$ and $t_{ext} = 13 \text{ in}$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 786.9 \text{ kips} (3500.3 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 79726 \text{ kip} - \text{ft} (108094 \text{ kN} - \text{m})$$

$$0.5 \frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.0$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$ and $t_{ext} = 14\text{in}$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 796.3\text{kips}(3542.1\text{kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 80680\text{kip} - \text{ft}(109387\text{kN} - \text{m})$$

$$0.5 \frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.0$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$ and $t_{ext} = 19\text{in}$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot b_w \cdot z \cdot v \cdot f'_{cd}}{\cot(\theta) + \tan(\theta)} = 798.9\text{kips}(3553.7\text{kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = 2v \cdot \alpha_c \cdot f'_{cd} \cdot A_o \cdot t \cdot \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 80943\text{kip} - \text{ft}(109744\text{kN} - \text{m})$$

$$0.5 \frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}} + \frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}} = 1.0$$

Since the whole cross section was adequate as calculated before, the calculations regarding the adequacy of the cross section finish here.

Step 11.4. Calculate the required shear reinforcement on exterior webs

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45° , 35° and 22° .

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.26\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(6.6\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.18\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(4.6\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.11\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(2.8\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 12. Calculate the required torsion reinforcement

The calculations will be developed for angles of 45° , 35° and 22° . The angle of inclination of exterior webs should be considered, therefore $\alpha = 27^\circ$.

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.04\text{in}^2/\text{in} \left(1.0\text{mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.03 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.8 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.02 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.5 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 13. Calculate the transverse reinforcement required for torsion on flanges

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.037 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.94 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.026 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.66 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.015 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.38 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 14. Calculate the longitudinal reinforcement required for torsion

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{tl}/s = \frac{T_u \cdot p_h \cdot \cot(\theta)}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd}} = 46.1 \text{ in}^2 \left(29742 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$A_{tl}/s = \frac{T_u \cdot p_h \cdot \cot(\theta)}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd}} = 65.8 \text{ in}^2 \left(42452 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$A_{tl}/s = \frac{T_u \cdot p_h \cdot \cot(\theta)}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_{yd}} = 114.0 \text{ in}^2 \left(73548.3 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

Step 15. Calculate the reinforcement on exterior webs, adding the required reinforcement for shear and torsion

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{total,ext}/s = \frac{A_{sw,ext}}{s} + \frac{A_{tw}}{s} = 0.30 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(7.62 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$A_{total,ext}/s = \frac{A_{sw,ext}}{s} + \frac{A_{tw}}{s} = 0.21 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(5.3 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$A_{total,ext}/s = \frac{A_{sw,ext}}{s} + \frac{A_{tw}}{s} = 0.12 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(3.1 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 16. Compute the required spacing for stirrups on exterior and interior webs

As stirrups, #5 (16mm) bars with an area of 0.31 in^2 (198 mm^2).

Interior webs:

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{sw}} = 2.75 \text{ in} (70 \text{ mm})$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{sw}} = 4 \text{ in} (100 \text{ mm})$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{sw}} = 7.25 \text{ in} (105 \text{ mm})$$

Exterior webs:

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{total,ext}} = 2.00 \text{ in} (50 \text{ mm})$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{total,ext}} = 2.75 \text{ in} (70 \text{ mm})$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{total,ext}} = 5 \text{ in} (125 \text{ mm})$$

Flanges:

For flanges #3 (10mm) stirrups with an area of 0.11 in^2 (71.3 mm^2)

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_f} = 6.50in(165mm)$$

For $\theta = 35^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_f} = 9.25in(235mm)$$

For $\theta = 22^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_f} = 12in(305mm)$$

Design computations according to AASHTO LRFD 2017 [3]

Step 1: Determine the factored bending moment, shear force, and torsional moment at the face of Bent 2 of the box-girder based on the load combinations

$$M_u^- = 60865.2kip - ft \ (82522kN - m) \text{ at the face of Bent 1}$$

$$M_u^- = 47683.3kip - ft \ (64650kN - m) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$V_u = 3268.3kip \ (4538.2kN) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$T_u = 13242.1kip - ft \ (17954kN - m) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

Step 2: Determine the section properties and material properties

Table 10—Section and material properties AASHTO LRFD 2017

SECTION PROPERTIES		
A_{cp}	44637 in ²	2.9×10^7 mm ²
p_{cp}	1275 in	32385 mm
A_g	13684 in ²	8.8×10^6 mm ²
d	64.8 in	1646 mm
d_s	77in	1956 mm
b_w	60 in	1524 mm
A_{oh}	41710 in ²	2.7×10^7 mm ²
p_h	1250 in	31750 mm
β_1	0.80	
k	0.28	
I	1.7×10^7 in ⁴	
y	39 in	
S_c	4.4×10^5 in ³	
γ_1	1.6	
γ_2	1.1	
γ_3	0.75	

Step 3: Calculate the cracking moment

$$M_{cr} = \gamma_3 \left[(\gamma_1 \cdot f_r + \gamma_2 \cdot f_{cpe}) S_c \right] = 54204.4kip - ft(73491.3kN - m)$$

$$M_r = \min(M_{cr}, 1.33M_u)$$

$$M_r = 54204.4kip-ft(73491.3kN-m)$$

Step 4: Compute the nominal resistance of the section based on the resistance provided by the prestressing steel

$$P_j = 9300\text{kip} (41369\text{kN})$$

$$c = \frac{A_{ps} \cdot f_{pu}}{0.85 f'_c \cdot \beta_1 \cdot b + k \cdot \frac{A_{ps} \cdot f_{pu}}{d}} = 6.85\text{in} (174\text{mm}) \quad f_{ps} = f_{pu} \cdot \left(1 - k \frac{c}{d}\right) = 262\text{ksi} (1807\text{MPa})$$

$$M_n = A_{ps} f_{ps} \left(d - \frac{\beta_1 \cdot c}{2}\right) = 62234\text{kip} - \text{ft} (84378\text{kN} - \text{m})$$

Step 5: Compute the nominal resistance providing mild steel

$$\text{Assuming } A_s = 40\text{in}^2 (25806.4\text{mm}^2)$$

$$a = \frac{A_{ps} \cdot f_{pu} + A_s \cdot f_y}{0.85 f'_c \cdot \beta_1 \cdot b + k \cdot \frac{A_{ps} \cdot f_{pu}}{\beta_1 \cdot d}} = 6.54\text{in} (166\text{mm}) \quad f_{ps} = f_{pu} \cdot \left(1 - k \frac{a}{\beta_1 \cdot d}\right) = 260.5\text{ksi} (1796\text{MPa})$$

$$M_n = A_{ps} f_{ps} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2}\right) + A_s f_y \left(d - \frac{a}{2}\right) = 76084.4\text{kip} - \text{ft} (103157\text{kN} - \text{m})$$

Step 6: Calculate the net longitudinal strain

$$d = \frac{M_n}{A_s f_y + A_{ps} f_{ps}} = 63.6\text{in} (1616\text{mm})$$

α is the angle of curvature of the tendon at the section calculated, for this case $\alpha = 0.026\text{rad}$

$$V_p = P_j \cdot \alpha = 241.8\text{kips} (1075.6\text{kN})$$

$$V_{eff} = V_u + \frac{T_u \cdot d}{2A_o} = 3440.9\text{kip} (15305.9\text{kN})$$

$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{\frac{|M_u|}{d_v} + 0.5N_u + |V_{eff} - V_p| - A_{ps} \cdot f_{po}}{2(E_s A_s + E_p A_{ps})} = 0.00071$$

Step 7: Calculate the values of θ and β

$$\beta = \frac{4.8}{1 + 750 \cdot \varepsilon_s} = 3.13$$

$$\theta = 29 + 3500 \cdot \varepsilon_s = 31.5^\circ$$

Step 8: Determine the transverse reinforcement required for shear

$$V_c = 0.0316\beta \cdot \lambda \sqrt{f'_c} \cdot b_w \cdot d = 843\text{kips} (3750\text{kN})$$

$$V_s = \frac{V_u}{\phi} - V_c - V_p = 2546.7\text{kip} (11328.3\text{kN})$$

$$A_{vs}/s = \frac{V_s}{f_y \cdot d \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.41\text{in}^2/\text{in} (10.4\text{mm}^2/\text{mm})$$

Step 9. Check if longitudinal reinforcement can resist the required tension

Equation 1:

$$A_{ps} \cdot f_{ps} + A_s \cdot f_y = 14362.2 \text{ kips}$$

Equation 2:

$$\frac{|M_u|}{d} + 0.5 \frac{N_u}{\phi} + \left(\left| \frac{V_{eff}}{\phi} - V_p \right| - 0.5V_s \right) \cot(\theta) = 12768.1 \text{ kips}$$

If Equation 1 > Equation 2 then the provided longitudinal reinforcement is adequate for resisting the required tension

Step 10. Determine the transverse reinforcement to be used on exterior girders

$$V_{u,ext} = 848.70 \text{ kips}$$

$$V_{eff,ext} = V_{u,ext} + \frac{T_u \cdot d}{2A_o} = 1021.3 \text{ kips} (4543 \text{ kN})$$

$$\varepsilon_{s,ext} = \frac{\frac{|M_u|}{5} + 0.5N_u + |V_{eff,ext} - V_p| - \frac{A_{ps}}{5} f_{po}}{2 \left(E_s \frac{A_s}{5} + E_p \frac{A_{ps}}{5} \right)} = 0.00105$$

$$\beta_{ext} = \frac{4.8}{1 + 750\varepsilon_s} = 3.13$$

$$\theta_{ext} = 29 + 3500\varepsilon_{s,ext} = 32.7^\circ$$

$$V_{c,ext} = 0.0316\beta \cdot \lambda \sqrt{f'_c} \cdot t_f \cdot d = 168.6 \text{ kips} (750 \text{ kN})$$

$$V_{s,ext} = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{\phi} - V_{c,ext} - V_{p,ext} = 726.1 \text{ kip} (3230 \text{ kN})$$

$$A_{vs,ext} = \frac{V_{s,ext}}{f_y \cdot d \cot(\theta)} = 0.122 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(78.7 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 11. Determine the amount of transverse reinforcement required for torsion on webs

$$A_t = \frac{\frac{T_u}{\phi}}{2f_y \cdot A_o \cot(\theta) \cos(\alpha)} = 0.03 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.76 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 12. Determine the amount of transverse reinforcement required for torsion on flanges

$$A_{tf} = \frac{\frac{T_u}{\phi}}{2f_y \cdot A_o \cot(\theta) \cos(\alpha)} = 0.025 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.64 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 12. Determine the amount of longitudinal reinforcement required for torsion

$$A_{lt} = \frac{\frac{T_u}{\phi} \cdot p_h}{2 \cdot A_o \cdot f_y} = 51.9 \text{ in}^2 \left(33483.8 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

Step 13. Determine the amount of transverse reinforcement to be used on the exterior webs

$$A_{total,ext} = A_t + A_{v,ext} = 0.151 \frac{in^2}{in} \left(3.84 \frac{mm^2}{mm} \right)$$

Step 14. Determine the spacing to be used for stirrups

Interior webs:

#5 (16mm) two legged stirrups will be used with an area $A_v = 0.61in^2$ (394mm²)

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{vs}} = 7.25in(185mm)$$

Exterior webs:

#5 (16mm) two legged stirrups will be used with an area $A_v = 0.61in^2$ (394mm²)

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_{vs,ext}} = 4in(100mm)$$

Flanges:

#3 (10mm) two legged stirrups will be used with an area $A_v = 0.22in^2$ (142mm²)

$$s = \frac{A_v}{A_f} = 8.50in(215mm)$$

Design computations according to Model Code MC-2010 [5]

Step 1: Determine the factored bending moment, shear force, and torsional moment at the face of Bent 2 of the box-girder based on the load combinations

$$M_u^- = 61102.3kip - ft \ (82844kN - m) \text{ at the face of Bent 1}$$

$$M_u^- = 47741.3kip - ft \ (64715kN - m) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$V_u = 3162.2kip \ (14066.2kN) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

$$T_u = 11354kip - ft \ (15394kN - m) \text{ at a distance } d \text{ of the face of Bent 1}$$

Step 2: Determine the section properties and material properties

Table 10—Section and material properties MC-2010

SECTION PROPERTIES		
A_{cp}	44637 in ²	2.9×10^7 mm ²
p_{cp}	1275 in	32385 mm
A_g	13684 in ²	8.8×10^6 mm ²
d	64.8 in	1646 mm
d_s	77in	1956 mm
b_w	60 in	1524 mm
A_{oh}	41710 in ²	2.7×10^7 mm ²
p_h	1250 in	31750 mm
MATERIAL PROPERTIES		
λ	1	
γ_c	1.50	
γ_s	1.15	
$f_{p,ud}$	235 ksi	1620.3 Mpa

$f_{y,d}$	52.2 ksi	360 Mpa
$f'_{c,d}$	3.33 ksi	23 Mpa
$f_{p0.1k}$	243 ksi	1676 Mpa
$f_{p,d}$	211.3 ksi	1457 Mpa

Step 3: Check the flexural resistance for the tendon layout shown in Fig. 6, based on the factored bending moment produced at the face of Bent 2.

$$\frac{M_u}{\phi} = A_{ps} f_{pd} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2} \right)$$

$$A_{ps} = \frac{P_j}{f_{pj}} = \frac{9300 \text{ kips}}{202.5 \text{ ksi}} = 46 \text{ in}^2 \quad \rho_p = \frac{A_{ps}}{A_g} = 0.00336$$

$$a = \frac{A_{ps} \times f_{pd}}{\lambda f_c \times b} = 5.63 \text{ in}$$

$$M_n = 46 \text{ in}^2 \times 211.3 \text{ ksi} \left(64.8 \text{ in} - \frac{5.63 \text{ in}}{2} \right) = 50127 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (67963.1 \text{ kN-m})$$

Step 4: Compute the additional mild steel required for flexure

$$M_n = A_{ps} f_{pd} \left(d_p - \frac{a}{2} \right) + A_s f_y \left(d - \frac{a}{2} \right)$$

$$\text{Assuming : } A_s = 40 \text{ in}^2 \quad (25806.4 \text{ mm}^2)$$

$$a = \frac{A_{ps} \times f_{pd} + A_s \times f_y}{\lambda f_c \times b} = 6.84 \text{ in}$$

$$M_n = 62433.2 \text{ kip-ft} \quad (84648 \text{ kN-m})$$

This area of reinforcement will correspond to 51 #8 (25 mm) bars.

Step 5. Determine the net longitudinal strain in the cross section

$$P_j = 9300 \text{ kips} \quad (41368.5 \text{ kN}) \quad e_p = d_p - 45.6 \text{ in} = 19.2 \text{ in}$$

$$z = \frac{(0.9 \cdot d)^2 \cdot A_s + (0.9 \cdot d_p)^2 \cdot A_{ps}}{(0.9 \cdot d) A_s + (0.9 \cdot d_p) \cdot A_{ps}} = 63.9 \text{ in} \quad (1623 \text{ mm})$$

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{\frac{M_u - P_j \cos(\alpha) \cdot e_p}{z} + V_u - P_j \sin(\alpha) + \left[0 - P_j \cos(\alpha) \cdot \left(\frac{0.9 d_p - e_p}{z} \right) \right]}{2 \left(\frac{0.9 d}{z} E_s \cdot A_s + \frac{0.9 d_p}{z} E_p \cdot A_{ps} \right)} = 0.000693$$

Step 6. Compute the maximum shear resistance and torsional resistance

For Level of Approximation 1

$$k_{eI} = 0.55$$

$$n_{fc} = \left(\frac{30 \text{ MPa}}{f'c} \right)^{1/3} = 0.96$$

$$k_{cI} = k_{eI}(n_{fc}) = 0.53$$

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{k_{c1} f'_c b_w z}{\gamma_c} \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 2570.5 \text{ kips} (11434.2 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = k_{c1} \frac{f'_c}{\gamma_c} t_f \cdot 2 \cdot A_k \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 47537 \text{ kip-ft} (64452 \text{ kN-m})$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{k_{c1} f'_c b_w z}{\gamma_c} \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 3241.3 \text{ kips} (14418 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = k_{c1} \frac{f'_c}{\gamma_c} t_f \cdot 2 \cdot A_k \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 59941 \text{ kip-ft} (81269 \text{ kN-m})$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{k_{c1} f'_c b_w z}{\gamma_c} \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 3355.6 \text{ kips} (14927 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = k_{c1} \frac{f'_c}{\gamma_c} t_f \cdot 2 \cdot A_k \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 62055 \text{ kip-ft} (84135 \text{ kN-m})$$

For Level of Approximation II

$$\varepsilon_{x1} = 0.001$$

$$\theta = 20 + 10000 \cdot \varepsilon_{x1} = 30^\circ$$

$$\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_{x1} + (\varepsilon_{x1} + 0.002) (\cot(\theta))^2 = 0.01$$

$$k_{e2} = \frac{1}{1.2 + 55\varepsilon_1} = 0.57 \quad k_{c2} = k_{e2} \cdot n_{fc} = 0.55$$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{k_{c2} f'_c b_w z}{\gamma_c} \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 3019.3 \text{ kips} (13430.5 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = k_{c1} \frac{f'_c}{\gamma_c} t_f \cdot 2 \cdot A_k \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 55835 \text{ kip-ft} (75702 \text{ kN-m})$$

For Level of Approximation III

$$\theta = 20 + 10000 \cdot \varepsilon_x = 27^\circ$$

$$\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_x + (\varepsilon_x + 0.002) (\cot(\theta))^2 = 0.009$$

$$k_{e2} = \frac{1}{1.2 + 55\varepsilon_1} = 0.59 \quad k_{c2} = k_{e2} \cdot n_{fc} = 0.57$$

$$V_{rd,max} = \frac{k_{c2} f'_c b_w z}{\gamma_c} \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 2928.4 \text{ kips} (13026.2 \text{ kN})$$

$$T_{rd,max} = k_{c1} \frac{f'_c}{\gamma_c} t_f \cdot 2 \cdot A_k \sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) = 54155 \text{ kip-ft} (73424 \text{ kN-m})$$

Step 7. Check if the dimensions of the cross section are adequate

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1.6$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 0.9$$

Level of Approximation II

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1.2$$

Level of Approximation III

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1.2$$

The dimensions of the cross section are adequate if $\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 \leq 1.0$ so then, the cross sections that not fulfill this requirement will be enlarged. This process is done iterating the values until the inequality is fulfilled.

For $\theta = 25^\circ$, $b_w = 74\text{in}$ (1880mm), $t_f = 16\text{in}$ (406mm)

$$V_{rd,max} = 3170.3\text{kips}(14102.2\text{kN}) \quad T_{rd,max} = 63382.7\text{kip-ft}(85935.4\text{kN-m})$$

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1.0$$

Level of Approximation II

$b_w = 65\text{in}$ (1651mm), $t_f = 13\text{in}$ (330mm)

$$V_{rd,max} = 3271\text{kips}(14550.1\text{kN}) \quad T_{rd,max} = 60488.1\text{kip-ft}(82010.8\text{kN-m})$$

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1.0$$

Level of Approximation III

$b_w = 65\text{in}$ (1651mm), $t_f = 13\text{in}$ (330mm)

$$V_{rd,max} = 3172.4\text{kips}(14111.5\text{kN}) \quad T_{rd,max} = 58668\text{kip-ft}(79543.1\text{kN})$$

$$\left(\frac{T_u}{T_{rd,max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_u}{V_{rd,max}}\right)^2 = 1.0$$

Step 8. Compute the minimum reinforcement

$$\rho_w = 0.08 \frac{\sqrt{f'_c}}{f_{yk}} = 0.0011$$

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_{v,\min} = \rho_{w,\min} b_w = 0.084 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(2.13 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_{v,\min} = \rho_{w,\min} b_w = 0.068 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(1.73 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{v,\min} = \rho_{w,\min} b_w = 0.068 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(1.73 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_{v,\min} = \rho_{w,\min} b_w = 0.074 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(1.90 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_{v,\min} = \rho_{w,\min} b_w = 0.074 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(1.90 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Step 9. Compute the area of transverse reinforcement for shear

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_v / s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.44 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(11.2 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_v / s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.73 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(18.5 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_v / s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.95 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(24.1 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_v / s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.55 \text{in}^2 / \text{in} \left(14.0 \text{mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_v/s = \frac{V_u}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.48 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(12.2 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 10. Check if longitudinal reinforcement can resist the required tension

Equation 1

$$A_{ps} f_{pd} + A_s f_{yd} = 11791.3 \text{ kip} (52450.3 \text{ kN})$$

Equation 2

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$\frac{V_u}{2} \cot(\theta) = 3391 \text{ kips} (15084 \text{ kN})$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$\frac{V_u}{2} \cot(\theta) = 2060.5 \text{ kips} (9165.6 \text{ kN})$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$\frac{V_u}{2} \cot(\theta) = 1581 \text{ kips} (7033 \text{ kN})$$

Level of Approximation II

$$\frac{V_u}{2} \cot(\theta) = 2738.5 \text{ kips} (12181.5 \text{ kN})$$

Level of Approximation III

$$\frac{V_u}{2} \cot(\theta) = 3113 \text{ kips} (13847.3 \text{ kN})$$

If Equation 1 > Equation 2 then the longitudinal steel provided could resist the required tension.

Step 11. Design the transverse reinforcement for shear for exterior webs

The ultimate shear load on exterior webs is $V_{u,ext} = 765.2 \text{ kips} (3403.8 \text{ kN})$.

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\frac{M_u - P_j \cos(\alpha) \cdot e_p}{5 \cdot z} + V_u - \frac{P_j}{5} \sin(\alpha) + \left[0 - \frac{P_j}{5} \cos(\alpha) \cdot \left(\frac{0.9d_p - e_p}{z} \right) \right]}{2 \left(\frac{0.9d}{z} E_s \cdot A_s + \frac{0.9d_p}{z} E_p \cdot A_{ps} \right)} = 0.000654$$

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.11 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(2.80 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.18 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(4.60 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.23 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(5.84 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.13 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(3.30 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_{v,ext}/s = \frac{V_{u,ext}}{z \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.12 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(3.05 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 12. Determine the amount of transverse reinforcement for torsion on exterior webs

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.020 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.51 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.032 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.813 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.041 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(1.04 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.024 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.610 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_t/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta) \cdot \cos(\alpha)} = 0.021 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.533 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 13. Determine the amount of transverse reinforcement for torsion on flanges

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.017 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.432 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.028 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.711 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.037 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.940 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.021 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.533 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_{tf}/s = \frac{T_u}{2A_k \cdot f_{yd} \cdot \cot(\theta)} = 0.019 \text{ in}^2/\text{in} \left(0.483 \text{ mm}^2/\text{mm} \right)$$

Step 14. Determine the amount longitudinal reinforcement for torsion

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_{tl} = \frac{\left(V_u + \frac{T_u \cdot z}{2A_k} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cot(\theta)}{f_{yd}} = 58.7 \text{ in}^2 \left(37871 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_{tl} = \frac{\left(V_u + \frac{T_u \cdot z}{2A_k} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cot(\theta)}{f_{yd}} = 35.7 \text{ in}^2 \left(23032.2 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{tl} = \frac{\left(V_u + \frac{T_u \cdot z}{2A_k} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cot(\theta)}{f_{yd}} = 27.4 \text{ in}^2 \left(17677.4 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_{tl} = \frac{\left(V_u + \frac{T_u \cdot z}{2A_k} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cot(\theta)}{f_{yd}} = 47.4 \text{ in}^2 \left(30581 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_{st} = \frac{\left(V_u + \frac{T_u \cdot z}{2A_k} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cot(\theta)}{f_{yd}} = 54.0 \text{ in}^2 \left(34839 \text{ mm}^2 \right)$$

Step 15. Determine the amount of transverse reinforcement to be used on exterior webs

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$A_{T,ext} = A_{v,ext} + A_t = 0.13 \text{ in}^2 / \text{in} \left(3.30 \text{ mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$A_{T,ext} = A_{v,ext} + A_t = 0.21 \text{ in}^2 / \text{in} \left(5.33 \text{ mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$A_{T,ext} = A_{v,ext} + A_t = 0.27 \text{ in}^2 / \text{in} \left(6.60 \text{ mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation II

$$A_{T,ext} = A_{v,ext} + A_t = 0.16 \text{ in}^2 / \text{in} \left(4.06 \text{ mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Level of Approximation III

$$A_{T,ext} = A_{v,ext} + A_t = 0.14 \text{ in}^2 / \text{in} \left(3.56 \text{ mm}^2 / \text{mm} \right)$$

Step 16. Calculate the spacing of transverse reinforcement

Interior webs

Use #5 (16mm) two legged stirrups with an area $A_{v,prov}$ of 0.61 in^2 (396 mm^2)

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_v} = 6.75 \text{ in}$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_v} = 4 \text{ in}$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_v} = 3 \text{ in}$$

Level of Approximation II

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_v} = 5.50 \text{ in}$$

Level of Approximation III

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_v} = 6.25in$$

Exterior webs

Use #5 (16mm) two legged stirrups with an area A_v of $0.61in^2$ ($396mm^2$)

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_{T,ext}} = 4.75in$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_{T,ext}} = 2.75in$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_{T,ext}} = 2in$$

Level of Approximation II

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_{T,ext}} = 3.75in$$

Level of Approximation III

$$s = \frac{A_{v,prov}}{A_{T,ext}} = 4.50in$$

Flanges

Use #5 (16mm) two legged stirrups with an area $A_{t,prov}$ of $0.61in^2$ ($396mm^2$)

Level of Approximation I

For $\theta = 25^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{t,prov}}{A_f} = 12in$$

For $\theta = 37.5^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{t,prov}}{A_f} = 7.75in$$

For $\theta = 45^\circ$

$$s = \frac{A_{t,prov}}{A_f} = 5.75in$$

Level of Approximation II

$$s = \frac{A_{t,prov}}{A_f} = 10.25in$$

Level of Approximation III

$$s = \frac{A_{t,prov}}{A_f} = 11.75in$$

Final results comparison

Table 11—Results comparison of gross concrete area and required transverse reinforcement.

Design Code	A_g disregarding overhanging flanges (ft ²)	Required transverse reinforce- ment for exterior web (shear and torsion) (in ² /in)	Required transverse reinforce- ment for interior web (shear) (in ² /in)	Required transverse reinforce- ment for flange (torsion) (in ² /in)	Required longitudinal reinforcement for flexure (in ²)	Required longitudinal reinforcement for torsion (in ²)
ACI 318-14	106.3	0.195	0.111	0.035	30	83.3
AASHTO LRFD 2017	95.1	0.151	0.082	0.026	40	52.0
EN 1992-2004 ($\theta = 45^\circ$)	95.1	0.295	0.208	0.034	40	46.1
EN 1992-2004 ($\theta = 35^\circ$)	95.6	0.207	0.146	0.026	40	65.8
EN 1992-2004 ($\theta = 22^\circ$)	106.5	0.119	0.084	0.015	40	114.0
MODEL CODE 2010 -LoA 1 ($\theta = 45^\circ$)	95.1	0.271	0.190	0.037	40	27.3
MODEL CODE 2010 -LoA 1 ($\theta = 37.5^\circ$)	95.1	0.208	0.146	0.029	40	35.6
MODEL CODE 2010 -LoA 1 ($\theta = 25^\circ$)	101.8	0.127	0.089	0.017	40	58.5
MODEL CODE 2010 -LoA 2	97.4	0.157	0.110	0.023	40	47.2
MODEL CODE 2010 -LoA 3	97.4	0.133	0.097	0.019	40	53.7

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